

PECULIARITIES OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ADAPTABILITY OF SCHOOLCHILDREN INVOLVED IN THE PROCESS OF BULLYING

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the determinants of socio-psychological adaptability of bullying in the school environment. Socio-psychological adaptability was studied using the questionnaire of K.Rogers and R. Diamond. The questionnaire has 6 integral indicators: adaptation, perception of others, internality, self-perception, emotional conformity, striving for dominance. The phenomenon of bullying is considered within the framework of the bullying structure (initiator, victim, assistant, observer, defender) and the risk of bullying (insecurity, well-being, disunity, equality). The results showed the peculiarities of the adaptability of schoolchildren. Initiators accept others, have an internal locus of control, experience emotional comfort and do not shy away from solving problems. Helpers do not accept themselves, are in conflict with others, experience emotional discomfort, and walk away from solving problems. Defenders accept themselves and accept others, have an internal locus of control, experience emotional comfort, do not walk away from problems.*

Keywords: *socio-psychological adaptability, bullying, bullying risk, bullying structure, adaptation, insecurity, school environment, initiator, victim, assistant, observer, defender.*

Introduction. Bullying is, by default, an unfavourable environment for the full development of schoolchildren. Prolonged stay in such an environment reduces the adaptive resource of an individual.

When defining the concept of ‘adaptation’ the researcher encounters very different interpretations depending on the emphasis on a certain aspect of the process. Adaptation has such types as: biological, physiological, psychological, social, socio-psychological and professional.

Each psychological school considers the term ‘socio-psychological adaptation’ differently for example, A.A.Nalchajyan, believed that this is a process of productive interaction between the individual and the group, which excludes the presence of conflicts[5].

The study of the features of socio-psychological adaptability in the process of bullying acquires special research and practical relevance precisely because of the increasing incidence of bullying in the school environment for the development of ways to counteract it.

Thus, the relevance of the work is determined by the need, firstly, for a deeper research study of the process of bullying in the school environment, and secondly, to identify the characteristics of bullying participants in terms of socio-psychological adaptability.

Literature review. In psychological science, the concept of ‘psycho-social adaptation’ is considered from the position of different schools: behavioural (J.Watson and others), cognitive (J.Piaget), psychoanalytical (E.Erikson, Z.Freud and others), humanistic (A.Maslow, C.Rogers and others)[4].

From the point of view of behaviourists, adaptation is considered as a process and as a state. Satisfaction of an individual's needs leads to changes in personality. Needs are conditioned by the influence of the environment.

From the point of view of psychoanalytical school, adaptation of personality is accompanied by individual's aspiration to homeostasis [1].

The adherents of the homomanistic orientation consider adaptation as a dynamic state of optimality. Consequently, adaptation is a model of a person's relations with the social environment and with himself. Thus, the subject acts as striving for its own development, capable of being responsible for its own behaviour.

In general, the concept of socio-psychological adaptation has such characteristics as: the relationship between the individual and the group, the absence of long-term external and internal conflicts, the satisfaction of their sociogenic needs, the state of self-assertion.

It is accepted to distinguish normal, deviant and pathological types of adaptation.

School bullying can lead to pathological or deviant types of adaptation. Initially the concept of bullying was considered as a pedagogical problem, but later the problem acquires a social character. Bullying is the process of prolonged harassment of one individual by a group of people. The very concept of bullying is first reflected in the works of Scandinavian scientist D. Olweus [5]. He defined bullying as harassment, discrimination, bullying.

School bullying is a systemic and complex phenomenon. In this regard, the method of response should be complex with the participation of parents, teachers and school psychologist. In this regard, our analysis was aimed at studying methods of prevention and counteraction to bullying used in other countries.

There are the following types of bullying: psychological, physical, direct and indirect. The most widespread type of bullying among young children is physical contact, to which every tenth child is exposed, and psychological bullying among adolescents. A significant proportion of bullying occurs among school-aged children, but cases of bullying can also be found in the adult environment: for example, in work collectives [2].

The negative consequences of bullying are reflected not only on the 'victims', but also on all participants of the process. Since bullying is a collective process, there is a peculiar role position in it. In the process of bullying, three sides of the relationship are usually distinguished: the aggressor, the victim and the observer. Systematic exposure to a traumatic situation leads to decreased academic motivation, refusal to attend school, symptoms of anxiety and depressive disorders, and increases the risk of suicidal behaviour, both in victims and in children who observe bullying.

Taking into account all the features of such a multifaceted concept, we decided to study the peculiarities of socio-psychological adaptability of school personality in the process of bullying. Studying the phenomenon of bullying from this angle will help to reveal the possibilities of revealing deeper features of the participants.

Research Methodology. The empirical study was based on the concept of socio-psychological adaptation of C. Rogers and R. Diamond.

The aim of the study was to investigate the possible inter-relationship of socio-psychological adaptability scales with indicators of bullying structure and bullying risk. The study involved middle school students of Tashkent city, 200 respondents aged from 11 to 17 years, including 99 boys and 101 girls. In order to study the following factors

1) socio-psychological adaptability - the method of diagnostics SPA of C.Rogers and R.Diamond in modification of A.M.Prikhozhan, developed with the position of humanistic approach, was used. The criteria of SPA are 6 integral indicators: adaptation, acceptance of others, internality, self-perception, emotional comfort, and aspiration to dominance.

2) bullying structure methodology - 'Bullying-structure' by E.G. Norkina was used to determine the presence of bullying role positions in the classroom. It consists of 25 questions, three of which allow to find out about the presence of bullying in the classroom, both by students and teachers. The author of the questionnaire took O.L. Glazman's classification as a basis.

3) bullying risk questionnaire - 'risk of bullying in school (ORB)' questionnaire of A.A. Bochaver, V.B. Kuznetsova, E.M. Bianchi, etc., and others. Including such scales as 'insecurity', 'well-being', 'dissociation', 'equality'. It is assumed that the most frequently selected response patterns in the classroom correspond to the existing classroom atmosphere and can be interpreted in terms of indicating subjectively experienced safety or insecurity and the corresponding risk of bullying[3].

The methods of analysis used were the Kraskal-Wallis test for independent samples and correlation analysis (Spearman). Statistical processing of data was performed using the SPSS 23.0 programme.

Analysis and results. Indicators of socio-psychological adaptability are the following indicators: self-acceptance- self-unacceptance, acceptance of others-conflict with others, internal locus of control-external locus of control, emotional comfort-emotional discomfort, dominance-dependence, avoidance of problem solving and sexual problems. The indicators of self-affirmation type were constructive type, destructive type and rejection of self-affirmation.

Differences in the indicators of bullying structure and socio-psychological adaptability (SPA) were obtained high values on the scale 'acceptance of others' ($H=14.815$, $p<0.05$), got the position of 'initiator' and low 'helper'. The results indicate that initiators have a need for communication. They believe that they have warm and good relations with others. Contact with strangers does not restrain them. Taking into account the data, we can say that such children often overestimate their self-image. They do not realise the negative consequences of their actions, or the act is not negative for them.

The data obtained according to the correlation coefficients between the indicators of bullying structure and socio-psychological adaptability (SPA) showed a negative relationship between the scale 'initiator' with the indicators: conflict with others ($r_s=-0.195$, $p<0.01$), external locus of control ($r_s=-0.222$, $p<0.01$), emotional discomfort ($r_s=-0.261$, $p<0.01$), avoidance of problem solving ($r_s=-0.249$, $p<0.01$). Hence, we can say that offenders do not perceive aggression as conflict. They are afraid to solve any problems at once. Excessive self-confidence prevents them from seeing their mistakes.

Negative correlation was revealed between the scale 'helper' and the following indicators: self-acceptance ($r_s=-0.200$, $p<0.01$), acceptance of others ($r_s=-0.202$, $p<0.01$), emotional comfort ($r_s=-0.164$, $p<0.05$). Also a positive relationship was found with the scales: non-acceptance of self ($r_s=0.173$, $p<0.05$), conflict with others ($r_s=0.206$, $p<0.01$), emotional discomfort ($r_s=0.180$, $p<0.01$), avoidance of problem solving ($r_s=0.139$, $p<0.05$). Helpers do not want the people around them to know his real, what is on their soul. They do not care about what happens to others, they are focused on themselves. Offenders are characterized by a sense of apathy and dislike of what surrounds them.

A positive correlation was found between the 'victim' scale and avoiding problem solving ($r_s=0.161$, $p<0.05$). Thus, it is characteristic of victims to run away from the problems that have arisen. They try to avoid cases that may cause them unpleasant experiences. It turns out that escape from solving problems makes the majority of schoolchildren victims of bullying.

Positive correlation was revealed between the scale 'observer' and the following scales: self-unacceptance ($r_s=0,227$, $p<0,01$), conflict with others ($r_s=0,240$, $p<0,01$), external locus of control ($r_s=0,167$, $p<0,05$), emotional discomfort ($r_s=0,250$, $p<0,01$). The tense atmosphere in the classroom pressurises the psyche of the observers. They become prone to negative experiences. There is a feeling of dissatisfaction with their personal qualities. The tendency to attribute the cause of what is happening to external factors dominates.

Positive correlation was found between the scale 'protector' and the following indicators: self-acceptance ($r_s=0,274$, $p<0,01$), acceptance of others ($r_s=0,172$, $p<0,05$), internal locus of control ($r_s=0,144$, $p<0,05$), emotional comfort ($r_s=0,183$, $p<0,01$). The defender scale is inversely related to the indicators: non-acceptance of self ($r_s=-0.378$, $p<0.01$), conflict with others ($r_s=-0.320$, $p<0.01$), external locus of control ($r_s=-0.228$, $p<0.01$), emotional discomfort ($r_s=-0.341$, $p<0.01$), addiction ($r_s=-0.198$, $p<0.01$), withdrawal from problem solving ($r_s=-0.178$, $p<0.05$), sex ($r_s=-0.156$, $p<0.05$). From this we concluded that defenders tend to analyze their feelings and actions. They always take responsibility for their actions. They accept others with all peculiarities. Protectors cannot be forced to do anything against their will. They are clearly aware of the personal boundaries of those around them. Always ready to help. Inner satisfaction with their actions causes a feeling of emotional comfort.

The results of the correlation coefficient between the indicators of bullying risk and SPA, revealed a positive correlation between the scale 'insecurity' and the indicators: conflict with others ($r_s=0.149$, $p<0.05$), dominance ($r_s=0.159$, $p<0.05$), avoidance of problem solving ($r_s=0.178$, $p<0.05$). Negative correlation was found between the scale 'dissociation' and acceptance of others ($r_s=-0.167$, $p<0.05$). The scale 'equality' is positively correlated with the factor of sexual problems ($r_s=0.144$, $p<0.05$).

The insecurity scale aims to explore students' subjective feelings in the classroom. Therefore, it is very logical to link insecurity with conflicts. A tense classroom atmosphere appears when: conflicts arise between pupils, one pupil dominates others against their will and there are no rational ways of solving problems.

Conclusion/Recommendations. Thus, the data analysis has shown that those who take the position of 'initiator' accept others, have an internal locus of control, experience emotional comfort and do not avoid solving problems.

Pupils occupying the position of 'helper' do not accept themselves, in conflict relations with others, experience emotional discomfort, go away from solving problems.

Pupils occupying the position of 'defender', accept themselves and accept others, have an internal locus of control, experience emotional comfort, do not withdraw from problems.

Children occupying the position of 'victim' are characterized by withdrawal from solving problems. Observers do not accept themselves, are in conflicting relationships with others, have an external locus of control, experience emotional discomfort.

The insecurity scale has a relationship with the scales: conflict with others, dominance, withdrawal from problem solving. The dissociation scale is related to the scale of non-acceptance of others, and the equality scale is related to the scale of sexual problems.

Pupils in the ‘helper’ position do not accept themselves, are in conflictual relationships and experience emotional discomfort, which contributes to avoiding problem solving. It is important to organize psychological support for these children, to help build self-esteem, and to develop effective conflict resolution and communication skills.

Pupils in the ‘victim’ position are characterised by avoidance of problem solving. It is important to work with them to build their self-confidence and develop their skills to actively participate in class life, and to help them reduce their anxiety and emotional discomfort. Working with a counsellor and developing problem-solving skills can have a significant impact on improving their social and emotional well-being.

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